

ISic0631

Inscribed base of statue group of the Pii Fratres

Language

Type

Material

Object

Editor

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Autopsy

2016.10.13

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Catania, inventory no inventory number

Physical Description

Two joining fragments from a statue base, extensively damaged on all sides. Parts of each original surface are preserved, such that it is possible to estimate the overall original dimensions. A substantial part of the front face is preserved, but the face is damaged on all sides except the lower edge. On the rear face four Latin letters over two lines and a part of the right marginal moulding are preserved from an earlier inscription (ISic3206).

Dimensions

Height 31 cm

Width 60 cm

Depth 47 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1-6: 25-35 mm

Interlineation

Line line1 to line1 : mm

Text

1. [FI] ḁmmiḁfugas fratr ę [S]
2. · pietatis maxima dona
3. · quos tulit hostilit [as]

4. · reddidit hos Merulus · v̄ (ir) [c (larissimus)]
5. · et spectabilis · consul [aris]
6. provinciae Sicilia e

Apparatus

Translation (en)

The flame-fleeing brothers, the greatest gifts of pietas, whom conflict carried off – these Merulus

has returned, vir clarissimus et spectabilis (most noble and respectable), consular governor of the province of Sicily.

Translation (it)

I fratelli in fuga dalle fiamme, i più grandi doni di pietas, che il conflitto portò via, questi

restaurò Merulus, uomo nobilissimo e rispettabile, governatore consolare della provincia di Sicilia.

Commentary

The inscription records the restoration of the famous statue group of the pii fratres by the Roman governor, Merulus, after their removal in a period of conflict. It is unknown whether this was a new statue group, or simply the restoration of the old one. Merulus is not otherwise known; his titles suggest a date after 434 AD. The conflict may have been the Vandal invasions of Sicily in 440-442, 455-468 and 491 AD. Archaeological research shows that the theatre was no longer in use by the very end of the fifth century AD, so the inscription probably dates shortly after either 442 or 468 AD.

The inscription on the reverse preserves the ends of two words, probably names, in letters of the high imperial period. It is possible that the text belongs to an earlier dedication of the same statue group, but it may have been something completely different, reused by Merulus. It is possible that this earlier base was originally in the nearby Roman forum.

Digital identifiers:

TM 175825

EDR 074112

EDCS 13600457

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